

HEIGHT ABOVE NEAREST DRAINAGE (HAND) MODEL AS A BASIS FOR FLOODPLAIN CLASSIFICATION AND ITS IMPLEMENTATION IN THE GEOHYDROAI PLATFORM

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The study applies the Height Above Nearest Drainage (HAND) model as a hydrologically consistent terrain descriptor for floodplain and landscape classification in the upper Prut–Cheremosh basin (Ukrainian Carpathians). HAND represents the vertical distance of each terrain cell from the nearest drainage line, reflecting the relative gravitational potential of runoff and enabling flood-prone area delineation using only Digital Elevation Models (DEMs).

Seven global DEMs—ALOS, ASTER, Copernicus DEM, FABDEM, NASADEM, SRTM, and TanDEM-X—were evaluated to analyze how vertical discrepancies affect HAND-derived inundation mapping. HAND rasters were generated after hydrological conditioning and flow routing (D8 algorithm, threshold = 500) using WhiteboxTools and Python. Validation was performed at the Yablunysia hydropost (597.815 m EVRS) to assess DEM vertical consistency. Results were visualized in the interactive GeoHydroAI Flood Scenarios web platform (www.geohydroai.org/flood_scenarios), which allows real-time comparison of HAND maps derived from multiple DEMs. Even 1–2 m elevation differences among DEMs significantly altered inundation extents. Integrating HAND into GeoHydroAI demonstrates an open, reproducible, and data-driven approach to floodplain mapping in mountainous regions.

Floods persist as among of the most frequent and destructive natural hazards in the mountainous regions of Ukraine, particularly within the upper Prut–Cheremosh basin. Recurrent extreme events cause geomorphological changes, infrastructure damage, and socio-economic losses. The complex topography of the Carpathians amplifies the nonlinear response of catchments to precipitation, making terrain representation crucial for hydrological modeling accuracy.

Accurate floodplain delineation depends critically on the quality of Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), which serve as the primary input for hydrological and hydraulic simulations. However, global DEMs (GDEMs) differ significantly in vertical accuracy, spatial resolution, and representation of surface features, as many reflect digital surface models (DSM) rather than bare-earth digital terrain models (DTM). Vegetation and built-up structures introduce systematic positive biases, leading to overestimation of elevation and errors in floodplain mapping.

To overcome these limitations, the Height Above Nearest Drainage (HAND) model offers a hydrologically normalized terrain metric by expressing the vertical distance of each grid cell above its nearest drainage channel. HAND captures the local gravitational potential of runoff and classifies terrain into floodplains, terraces, and valley slopes based solely on topographic information.

The objectives of this study were to:

- (i) evaluate the vertical consistency among seven global DEMs under uniform hydrological conditions;
- (ii) assess the sensitivity of HAND-based floodplain classification to elevation discrepancies; and
- (iii) demonstrate the integration of HAND in the GeoHydroAI Flood Scenarios platform for open and reproducible flood-risk mapping in the Carpathians.

The study area covers the upper Prut–Cheremosh basin, a mountainous region characterized by steep slopes, dense forests, and frequent flash floods. The following global DEMs were analyzed: ALOS AW3D30, ASTER GDEM v3, Copernicus DEM (GLO-30), FABDEM, NASADEM, SRTM v3, and TanDEM-X 90 m. All DEMs were resampled to 30 m resolution, vertically harmonized to the European Vertical Reference System (EVRS), and geoid-corrected (EGG2015) when necessary.

Each DEM underwent hydrological conditioning in WhiteboxTools, including sink filling, depression breaching, and flow enforcement to ensure continuous drainage. Flow routing was computed with the D8 algorithm, and stream networks were extracted using a flow-accumulation threshold of 500 cells. HAND rasters were generated with the *ElevationAboveStream* algorithm, which calculates the vertical distance from each cell to its nearest drainage line along the downslope flow path.

The GeoHydroAI Flood Scenarios web platform (www.geohydroai.org/flood_scenarios) was developed using Python (Dash, Terracotta tile server) for the backend and TypeScript (React, DeckGL) for the frontend visualization. It enables DEM comparison, HAND visualization, and real-time flood simulation. The platform integrates slope and HAND histograms, statistical summaries, and flood extent mapping, providing full reproducibility of hydrological analyses.

Among the analyzed DEMs, FABDEM and Copernicus DEM (GLO-30) showed the best vertical consistency with reference elevations (Yablunytsia hydropost). These DEMs also produced HAND rasters with smooth transitions and minimal artifacts in valley bottoms. ASTER and ALOS systematically overestimated elevations in forested zones, while SRTM and NASADEM performed moderately well.

Even small elevation discrepancies (1 m) between DEMs significantly influenced floodplain delineation, shifting HAND thresholds and changing inundation areas by in lowland zones. This highlights the sensitivity of HAND to vertical errors and the necessity of DEM validation prior to hydrological modeling.

The GeoHydroAI platform successfully visualized these differences, allowing users to interactively compare inundation scenarios, modify terrain features, and observe real-time effects. This open-source environment demonstrated the value of integrating DEM quality assessment with operational flood modeling.

The research confirmed that the HAND model is an efficient and hydrologically meaningful method for floodplain classification in mountainous environments. It enables rapid mapping of flood-prone zones using only elevation data, without requiring direct hydrological inputs.

Among the global DEMs tested, FABDEM and Copernicus DEM (GLO-30) achieved the highest vertical consistency with ground truth, whereas ASTER and ALOS tended to overestimate elevations in forested areas. Even minor vertical errors (1–2 m) resulted in substantial variations in HAND-derived flood boundaries.

Integrating HAND into the GeoHydroAI Flood Scenarios platform provides a transparent, reproducible, and interactive framework for flood-risk assessment and scenario visualization, bridging the gap between DEM validation, hydrological modeling, and real-time communication of flood hazards.

The comparative analysis demonstrated that HAND-derived flood extents are highly sensitive to the vertical accuracy and preprocessing of DEMs. In mountain basins such as the Prut–Cheremosh, even sub-meter errors can propagate into significant deviations in modeled flood boundaries. Therefore, DEM validation and hydrological conditioning are essential prerequisites for reliable HAND-based flood mapping.

Future work will focus on:

- Automated DEM accuracy validation using ICESat-2 altimetry;
- Coupling HAND with HEC-RAS 2D hydraulic modeling;
- Expanding GeoHydroAI to predict landscape changes under climate variability.

References

- Nobre, A. D., Cuartas, L. A., Hodnett, M. G., Rennó, C. D., Rodrigues, G., Silveira, A., & Tomasella, J. (2011). Height Above the Nearest Drainage: A hydrologically relevant new terrain model. *Journal of Hydrology*, 404(1–2), 13–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2011.03.051>
- Hawker, L., Neal, J., Bates, P. D., & Rougier, J. (2022). FABDEM: Global 30 m DEM with forests and buildings removed. *Scientific Data*, 9, 409. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac4d4f>
- GeoHydroAI. (2025). *Global DEM Accuracy Dashboard: Ukrainian Carpathians*. GeoHydroAI Platform. Available online: www.geohydroai.org/flood_scenarios
- WhiteboxTools: <https://www.whiteboxgeo.com/whitebox-workflows-for-python/> (<https://github.com/jblindsay/whitebox-tools/tree/master>)
- Denker, H. (2015). *A new European gravimetric (quasi)geoid EGG2015*. Poster presented at the XXVI General Assembly of the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG), Prague, Czech Republic. https://www.ife.uni-hannover.de/uploads/tx_tkpublikationen/IUGG_2015_EGG2015.pdf
- Tavares da Costa, R., et al. (2019). Comparative evaluation of HAND and hydraulic models for flood mapping in data-scarce regions. *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, 12(S1), e12522. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfr3.12522>
- Rennó, C. D., Nobre, A. D., Cuartas, L. A., Soares, J. V., Hodnett, M. G., Tomasella, J., & Waterloo, M. J. (2008). HAND, a new terrain descriptor using SRTM DEM: Mapping terra-firme rainforest environments in Amazonia. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 112(12), 3469–3481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2008.03.018>

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